

Improving the Quality of Open Funding Metadata: A Call to Action

Background and Detailed Recommendations

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Introduction

This document is the result of a [roundtable workshop](#) co-organized by the [Barcelona Declaration Working Group on Funding Metadata](#) and [Crossref](#) to discuss the challenges and opportunities for improving open funding metadata. Representatives from different stakeholder groups, including funders, publishers, and infrastructure providers, came together for a candid discussion about current barriers and opportunities for joint solutions. Improving the quality of open funding metadata requires improving how this information is captured, structured, and shared across the scholarly communication ecosystem.

The recommendations presented here reflect the collective expertise and commitment of the participants to build a more transparent, interoperable, and efficient funding metadata ecosystem. This document provides an overview of what open funding metadata is, why it matters, the current barriers to quality and coverage, and concrete actions that each stakeholder group can take to achieve this shared goal.

Document Outline

1. What Is Open Funding Metadata in Research?
2. Why Does Open Funding Metadata Matter?
3. What Do We Want?
4. Who Does What? Responsibilities across Stakeholders
5. What Are the Barriers?
6. Recommendations by Stakeholder

1. What Is Open Funding Metadata in Research?

Open funding metadata is [open research information](#) that refers to structured information on research funding and grants. It typically includes the funder's name or identifier, grant identifiers, and additional information about the grant, such as funding amount, beneficiaries and funding program(s).

In this document, we distinguish two types of open funding metadata: 1) information on funders and grants included in metadata for research outputs and 2) structured information about grants as standalone metadata.

- **Information on funders and grants** included in metadata for research outputs is collected by publishers – either at submission and / or extracted from full text – and typically includes the funder's name and / or identifier and grant identifiers. Publishers make this available in [Crossref](#) or [DataCite](#), enabling researchers, institutions, funders, and governments to identify publications linked to specific funders or grants.
- **Structured information about grants as standalone metadata** is provided by funders through their own databases, APIs, or by registering Grant DOIs. It typically includes the grant number, descriptions, funder information, and program details, and may also cover grant amounts, duration, and beneficiaries including [ORCID](#) iDs.

Both types can be linked to improve capture and usability. Authors use Grant DOIs to unambiguously identify funding in acknowledgments. When publishers include Grant DOIs in publication metadata, the full grant record can be retrieved from a central, standardized source across funders.

2. Why Does Open Funding Metadata Matter?

Open funding metadata is essential for building a more trustworthy, equitable and efficient research ecosystem. When provided in structured, machine-readable formats and accompanied by persistent identifiers, it unambiguously links funding to the correct researchers, organizations, projects and outputs. This connection enables these resources to be discovered, evaluated, and reused at scale. Furthermore, making this information openly available reduces administrative burden and reporting errors, improves interoperability across repositories, Current Research Information Systems (CRIS), and funder systems, and supports evidence-informed policy.

Open funding metadata delivers concrete benefits for various stakeholders across the research ecosystem:

- **Researchers** gain enhanced discoverability and recognition of their work through clearer links between funded projects and outcomes. Over time, this could also reduce the reporting burden on researchers, as funders may be able to directly retrieve information on funded output from open metadata sources.
- **Funders** benefit from transparent evidence of the reach and effectiveness of their investments, enabling them to monitor funding outcomes, make evidence-based decisions, track policy implementation, and strengthen accountability for their spending. When funding metadata is openly available and linked through persistent identifiers, funders can also retrieve information on research outputs directly from open infrastructures, reducing the need for manual reporting by researchers.
- **Publishers** benefit from more complete funding metadata as it clarifies the financial support of the research they publish. It helps publishers verify the provenance and integrity of submitted articles, where funding metadata is increasingly seen as a 'trust signal' for published content. It also enables them to better serve authors by improving the discoverability of their work.
- **Society at large** benefits from open funding metadata through greater transparency, stronger accountability, and more efficient use of resources, optimizing the effectiveness of funding allocations. Public access to information on how money is spent on research supports trust in science and enables scrutiny of potential conflicts of interest.
- **Open infrastructures** benefit from the availability of open funding metadata by increasing their coverage and improving data quality. Standardized metadata enables them to connect funders, institutions, and repositories more effectively, creating more efficient workflows and reducing duplication across the research information ecosystem.

3. Who Does What? Responsibilities across Stakeholders

To achieve the benefits of open funding information, stakeholders across the research ecosystem all have a role to play:

- **Researchers** include information about funding in the acknowledgments of their publications (clearly identifying who benefited from what funding) and / or enter the information into publisher submission systems when prompted.
- **Funders** provide clear and explicit instructions to authors how to acknowledge the funding received. When funders register Grant DOIs and accompanying metadata, they should instruct authors to use these Grant DOIs when acknowledging funding. Funders also provide open metadata (via their own websites, APIs, Grant DOIs or other systems) on their research grants and funding programs.
- **Publishers** collect information about funders and grants from authors through their submission systems and / or via extraction from full text. The collected information ideally contains PIDs such as Grant DOIs and Funder/ [ROR](#) IDs. Where this is not the case, publishers attempt to link funder names to Funder / [ROR](#) IDs. Finally, publishers include funding information (including Funder / [ROR](#) IDs and Grant DOIs) in funding acknowledgments and in publication metadata when registering DOIs for their publications.
- **Open Infrastructures** enable, collect, and display complete funding information and link it to the correct researchers, organizations, projects and outputs, using PIDs wherever possible. They may also programmatically match unstructured funding and grant metadata where needed, to augment the publisher- and funder-contributed metadata.

4. What Do We Want?

Our goal is to improve the quality and flow of open funding metadata across the scholarly communication ecosystem. This requires sustainable, accurate funding metadata capture at submission and across publication workflows, in ways that reduce researcher burden and enable reliable integration with open infrastructures. It also requires provision of open funding metadata on grants and funding programs by funders.

Reaching this goal requires improvements in the following areas:

- **Adoption of globally openly resolvable persistent identifiers**, such as [ROR](#) IDs & Grant DOIs
- **Funding metadata capture** at the point of entry in publication workflows
- **Standardization of funding metadata practices**, particularly in publication workflows: at submission as well as in production.
- **Coordination of the roles and responsibilities** among funders, publishers, submission systems, and infrastructure providers
- **Author experience in providing funding information**, including clarity of requirements and ease of use
- **Consistent and scalable practices for funders** regarding funding acknowledgments and Grant DOI adoption
- **Affordability and long-term sustainability** of technological solutions for funding metadata capture and propagation across systems.

5. What Are the Barriers?

What are the main obstacles to improving the quality and flow of funding metadata? During the roundtable session, participants identified three broad categories of barriers.

Lack of Standardization

Participants consistently pointed to the absence of shared standards as a major obstacle, affecting how funding information is captured, reported, and integrated across systems.

- There is no widely adopted standard for how funding information should be reported in acknowledgment sections (funders and grants), making it difficult to consistently capture and translate this information into structured funding metadata. Individual initiatives exist, such as that of [cOAlition S](#), which asks authors to acknowledge funding in a unified way; however, this is limited to a specific group of funders.
- Authors often provide incomplete or inconsistent funding information, reducing the accuracy of funding metadata and making it difficult for publishers to extract funding information in a standardized way.
- Workflows depend heavily on submission systems and local editorial practice. Some publishers collect funding data at submission, others don't enforce it consistently.
- Limited adoption of globally unique and persistent grant identifiers (such as Grant DOIs) among funders hinders the consistent identification and linking of funding information.
- Multiple sources of funding information (submissions, acknowledgments, funders) are not always aligned.
- Submission forms are often unintuitive and inconsistent across journals; with funding information often being optional.

Disconnected Systems

Platforms and systems often fail to communicate effectively with each other, creating significant friction in the funding metadata workflow.

- Limited integration between systems used in publisher production workflows leads to funding metadata being lost as information moves between systems.
- Inconsistent practices in how submission systems capture and enforce funding metadata can lead to incomplete coverage of funding metadata across publishers.

- Internal funder platforms, like grant management systems, are often disconnected from open PID infrastructures, preventing automatic linking of grants to outputs and researchers, as well as the lack of interoperability of funding metadata itself (e.g. grant information like grant amounts, beneficiaries, time periods, etc.).
- Migration to [ROR](#) and alignment with existing systems (e.g., Ringgold, OFR) and platform changes (e.g., Silverchair) are possible, but they require extensive internal work and have associated costs.

Costs, Culture and Capacity

Beyond technical challenges, cultural norms and capacity constraints pose substantial challenges to funding metadata capture and sharing.

- Funding metadata is not yet a community expectation. Legislation (e.g. EU / US Accessibility Acts) shows how regulation can drive change (similar levers could help here).
- Competing priorities mean funding metadata work only rises on the agenda when it aligns with multiple stakeholders' needs.
- A lack of clear and compelling value propositions for Grant DOIs and rich grant metadata limits their adoption across the community.
- Under-resourced publishers face difficulties in collecting and curating funding metadata.
- Responsibility for linking research outputs to grants largely falls on researchers. While this may be considered good scientific practice, it is often perceived as an administrative burden, which can lead to incomplete or inaccurate information.

6. Recommendations by Stakeholder

There is clear momentum and genuine willingness across the research ecosystem to improve open funding metadata. The actions below – collected at the roundtable workshop – outline both immediate steps that individual organizations can take and longer-term efforts that will depend on coordinated action. While each stakeholder group has specific responsibilities, many of these improvements will only succeed through alignment across the ecosystem. These recommendations are intended as a starting point for action, adaptable to each organization's context and capabilities.

Publishers

- **Optimize method(s) for capturing funding information.** While there is no one-size-fits-all solution regarding the timing and method of capturing funding information, the following approaches are suggested:
 - Make funding information, including Grant DOI, at submission a **mandatory field**.
 - Develop or adopt new tools for **structured funding metadata extraction from full text manuscripts**.
 - Ensure that submission and production systems include **mechanisms to validate and cross-check author-provided funding information** against both acknowledgment sections and data provided by funders (e.g. grantee information associated with Grant DOIs).
 - Reduce burden on authors through **automation and UX improvements**.
- **Follow standardized practice**
 - Require that authors provide a **funding statement** either in their acknowledgments or (preferably) as a separate funding statement in their publication.
 - Require clear **attribution of funding at the author level** (e.g. linking individual authors to specific grants), to identify who benefited from which funding.
 - Collaborate with funders on **standardization of funding acknowledgments**, including provision of structured information.
 - Follow **JATS4R recommendations** when capturing funding metadata (to aid reproducibility and interoperability).
 - Work with standards bodies like NISO to contribute to and evolve **shared guidelines for funding metadata**.

- Develop **standardized practices for submission** of funding metadata and Grant DOIs.
- **Strengthen journal production workflows to improve the quality and interoperability of funding metadata**
 - Raise awareness among editorial and production teams about the **importance of collecting and correctly handling funding information** during publication workflows.
 - **Improve flow and retention of metadata** through submission, production, and hosting systems.
 - **Use ROR IDs** instead of (or in addition to) closed identifier systems within production workflows to ensure consistent identification of organizations in funding metadata and support interoperability with downstream research information systems.
 - Ensure **appropriate quality assurance mechanisms** are in place when extraction and deposition of funding metadata are outsourced to third parties.

Publishing System Providers

- **Enable system functionalities for capturing and transferring funding metadata.**
Design and optimize system functionalities for capturing and transferring funding metadata across submission, production, and external systems, ensuring that these capabilities are consistently available to publisher clients.
 - Developing new tools for **structured funding metadata extraction from full text manuscripts**, possibly using AI.
 - **Implement ROR IDs** within systems (as replacement for or in addition to other identifier systems) to support consistent identification and interoperability.
- **Collaborate with other stakeholders** to improve processes and workflows.
 - Collaborate with **publisher** clients to facilitate the use of system functionalities, improve existing functionalities and develop new ones (see above).

Open Infrastructure Providers / PID Registries

- Advance **shared standards and tools** for funding metadata:
 - Develop matching strategies to link funder IDs with **ROR** IDs and Award IDs / funding with Grant DOIs.
 - Provide open-source extractors and APIs to deliver these matched / enriched relationships.

- Explore or extend services like [Crossref's landing-page generator](#) to lower the barrier for funders to implement Grant DOIs.
- Allow publishers to deposit **raw funding information** from the acknowledgment section alongside structured funding metadata in publication metadata.
- Consider having a way to capture the fact that a research output was not (externally) funded by allowing the registration of **“no external funding”**.
- Update guidelines for publishers / metadata schema to clearly differentiate between research funding and **publication funding**.

Funders

- **Share metadata** on grants and funding programs as openly and complete as possible in a structured machine-readable way, by means of open APIs, Grant DOIs or other systems.
- Consider **creating DOIs for grants**, for instance through the Grant Linking System provided by [Crossref](#), or through similar services offered by other DOI agencies such as [DataCite](#).
- **Mandate** acknowledgment of research funding as part of formal **grant conditions** and output sharing policies, and be as specific as possible about these requirements in communications with grant holders.
- Include the obligation to register funding metadata with [Crossref](#) (and other PID registries) in policy guidelines and **mandates for publishers**, following the model of the [Technical Guidance and Requirements for Plan S](#).
- Work with national / regional library consortium to ensure that open funding metadata is included as a minimum requirement in **publisher negotiations**.
- Collectively as funders improve **standardization** in the way researchers acknowledge research funding in research outputs by:
 - Creating a **standardized text** for funding acknowledgment sections (see e.g. cOAlition S).
 - based on a shared framework / ontology of funding organizations, funding programs, and awards.
 - make it easier for authors to make use of this standard by working with [Crossref](#), [DataCite](#) and other DOI agencies to include it as a metadata field of Grant IDs.

- Work with standards bodies like **NISO** and **JATS** on funding metadata guidelines.
- Explore ways to **reduce the burden on researchers** when reporting the outputs of their funding.
 - Support (the development of) systems to automatically link outputs to Grant DOI's.
 - Use available information from open infrastructures (avoid manual author entry).

Institutions and Libraries

- Include funding metadata in **negotiations with publishers** to ensure high-quality metadata across the scholarly communication system.
- Work with funders to develop **benchmark figures** (e.g. metrics on current levels of funding metadata coverage or completeness) to be used in these negotiations. As a minimum, require that funding information that is disclosed in funding acknowledgments is registered as metadata with [Crossref](#).
- Support the work of the **Joint Task Force on Negotiating Openness of Publication Metadata** installed by the Barcelona Declaration and OA2020 to exchange best practices in negotiating (funding) metadata.

In Conclusion: Moving Forward Together

There is clear momentum and genuine willingness among funders, publishers, and infrastructure providers to improve the availability and quality of open funding metadata. The barriers identified - spanning standardization, interoperability, culture, and capacity - are substantial but not insurmountable. While each stakeholder group has specific responsibilities, many improvements will only succeed through coordinated action - the development of shared standards, for instance, depends on publishers, funders, and infrastructure providers working in concert. Some of these actions will be taken up by the Barcelona Declaration Working Group on Funding Metadata, which will continue to serve as a forum for collective progress while individual organizations can adopt recommendations to their own context and capabilities.

Colofon

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